

KEY INDICATORS

With 2,711,567 hectares under organic management, France ranked second (after Spain) in terms of area under organic management, and 17% of the EU's organic farmland was in France. With 10.1% of its farmland being organic, France was slightly below the EU average of 11.1%. Growth from 2001 to 2024 was at almost 600%, thus higher than in the European Union. Regarding organic retail sales, with 12,176 million euros, France held rank two in the EU in 2024. With 5.7%, it had an above-EU-average organic share of the total food market.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2024

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

419,750 ha (1.5%)

2,711,567 ha (10.1%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2024

546%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2024

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

94,045 ha (0.6%)

1,396,743 ha (7.7%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

21,903 ha (2.1%)

249,619 ha (23.6%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

275,105 ha (2.7%)

249,619 ha (11%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

8,955 † (4.7%) (2020)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2024

Producers (Share of Total)

10,364 (1.7%)

61,886 (15.8%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

109

Processors

5,400

20,493

Importers

N/D

1,163

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2024

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

1,150 M €

12,176 M€ (5.7%)

Per Capita Consumption

18.9 €

177.8 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2024

958%

Imports

N/D

195,843 †

Source: FIBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN FRANCE

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey, based on AgenceBio, Eurostat and Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN FRANCE

Source: Agence Bio, Observatoire Bio

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

In the previous period, France halted maintenance payments, which contributed to the low share of certified organic land supported. Some regions continued with previous period maintenance payments until 2025. In mainland France, support for maintenance was reintroduced as part of the national eco-scheme. This support was extended to land in conversion, in addition to the P2 conversion payments. The contrasting approaches to conversion and maintenance support lead to some very large differences in payments for some land uses. Although the expenditure per hectare is planned to remain relatively constant, the increased area supported is expected to lead to more than 3 times the annual expenditure compared with the previous period. Some regional governments and water agencies provide top-up support that is not included here. Actual maintenance payments were reduced to 92 €/ha in 2023 and 96 €/ha in 2024 due to high eco-scheme demand, but are to be restored back to planned levels subsequently. Funds planned for conversion have been allocated elsewhere due to limited demand. Funding for Agence Bio activities has also been cut back in 2025.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	1,040 kha	3,384 kha (+225%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	3.6%	11.7% (+225%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	51%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	180 M€	603 ¹ M€ (+235%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	173 €	178 € (+3%)

¹Planned expenditure values for FR eco-schemes have been estimated from per hectare rates and R29 indicators

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027

ORGANIC SHARE

Organic Farming Support (P1/P2)	2,725 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	8,558 M€	24.2%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	2,718 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	49,742 M€	5.5%

Organic eco-scheme expenditure estimated from per hectare rates and R29 indicators. Regional top-up funding not included *including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	130	300	450	900	350
	2023	P2+P1	130 / +110	350 / +110	450 / +110	900 / +110	350 / +110
Change from 2019 to 2023			0%	+17%	0%	0%	0%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	0	0	0	0	0
	2023	P1/P2	110	110	110	110	110
Change from 2019 to 2023			∞	∞	∞	∞	∞
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		∞	∞	∞	∞	∞
	2023	P2+P1	+118%	+318%	+409%	+818%	+318%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing. P2 used for maintenance in Corsica and overseas territories. P2 maintenance in mainland France stopped from 2018. P1 eco-scheme also applies to land in conversion. Regional and water agency top-up funding not included.

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

France has had four national organic action plans since the first one was published in 1997. The latest one was published in 2024. In the previous plan, particular emphasis was placed on training, research and market information actions. The current action plan aims to address some of the challenges faced by the French organic sector since 2022. The 20% of public procurement and private catering (since 2024) organic requirement is part of the ÉGalim law.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2018-22	15% of UAA by 2022	20% of public procurement by 2022 (ÉGalim)
Current Action Plan	2024-30	18% of UAA by 2027	20% of public procurement required from 2022, and of private catering from 2024 (ÉGalim)

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2015 - 2022)

PRODUCTION
Increase support levels and awareness of funding sources; support group conversion, access to land, producers affected by external contamination; support development in overseas territories.

MARKETS
Identify sector development priorities; liaison meetings with market actors; develop options to deliver 20% public procurement goal, incl. best practice guidelines; increase hospitality catering, incl. staff training; promote exports; clarify use of AB logo with organic/ environmental certification; adapt regulations esp. for plant/ animal health.

INFORMATION
Agence Bio consumer promotion campaign; explain organic characteristics, benefits; consolidate/ facilitate access to technical, economic, ecological, social information for producers; integrate organic in sustainable production courses; multiple training initiatives; strengthen organic research, incl. in INRA Metaprogramme; define new mandate for Organic Research Council; develop Agence Bio statistical information; complete geolocation of organic land parcels to facilitate data exchange; regional market observatories.

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2024 - 2030)

PRODUCTION
Support organic conversion, maintenance under CAP; encourage participation in Future Agriculture (PLOA) and Business Growth/Transformation (PACTE) actions; promote access to land.

MARKETS
Better understand consumer demand and commercial catering practices; promote 20% public procurement (ÉGalim); develop sourcing for private caterers; promote distribution systems; consolidate/ develop resilient regional sectors; structure sectors for fair value distribution; strengthen use of contracts and regulatory tools; investment in modern production, processing tools.

INFORMATION
Communicate with general public, public catering actors, commercial catering (€8 m. allocated to Bioréflexe campaign in 2024); study economics of organic supply chains; improve market data collection with interprofessional organisations; understand/promote organic in regions; develop training incl. apprenticeships, continuing education, network of organic educational providers, training for caterers; research environmental, health, socio-economic impacts; dialogue on societal developments impacting sector; improve research dissemination; share knowledge with conventional; expand research, incl. tools for climate mitigation, adaptation; reduce/ manage risks of contamination; strengthen sustainability through transparency, anticipate new inputs (€8.7 m. for Fonds Avenir Bio projects in 2025).

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in France is almost 5%. Organic aquaculture has been supported as part of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture, including investment aids, conversion support, promotion and research. Aquaculture was not highlighted in the previous national organic action plan. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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